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**INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL-SEMINAR
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геомагнитной обстановкой, проведении цифровой фильтрации измеренных данных при работе в условиях с большим уровнем техногенных электромагнитных помех.

Создан пакет оригинальных компьютерных программ, позволяющих производить цифровую фильтрацию получаемых данных в условиях, где уровень техногенных помех в несколько раз превышает уровень реального сигнала. Постоянно пополняется банк данных по зарегистрированным в условиях города магнитным бурям.

Слежение за окружающей электромагнитной обстановкой в реальном времени помогает практической медицине в оказании своевременной помощи людям, подверженным повышенной чувствительности к изменениям магнитного поля в период геомагнитосферных возмущений и бурь.

(13)

7R5-M

EXPERIENCE OF MULTIPARAMETRICAL MONITORING REALIZATION IN CLINIC CONDITIONS

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As the beginning of active practical using of magnetometric devices in urban conditions have served created by us in the beginning of 90-th years experimental models of compact and reliable diagnostic magnetometers (DM), capable to work in conditions with a large level of industrial noises in urban environment. Created late the DM of the MAGIC series were successfully used for realization of electromagnetic monitoring in conditions of Moscow, Yalta and Kislovodsk cities clinics.

The DM, installed in reanimation branch of Central Railway Hospital (CRH) No.3 of Moscow, worked on continuous conditions more than 6 years, that has allowed us to conduct the whole number of work as methodical, as research character, to produce the necessary recommendations for detecting and treatment of magnetodepending cardiological sick peoples. Use the DM has allowed to organize a monoparametrical monitoring in clinic, that is to create own monitoring continuous service for environmental electromagnetic conditions in real time, has allowed to have really data on a current disturbance of a magnetic field, in good time to conduct a therapy of magnetodepending sick peoples at the beginning of magnetic storm and to give the necessary information in the town press.

At present time in the CRH small-sized IMPEDANCE digital data logger system of the IDL-04 -type (magnetic activity recorder) is used, which permits to conduct a multiparametrical monitoring of an environment by eight measuring channels. Main measuring channel is a magnetometrical channel, there is a opportunity of demonstration of current and stored data, realization of a digital optimum filtration of data, calculation and visualization of K-index of magnetic activity, manufacturing "hard-copy" storaged data at the help of a printer. Other measuring channels are used for connection of

electrical field sensors, for connection of temperature, atmospheric pressure and humidity sensors and etc.

Experience accumulated by us has shown, that the devices of such class can be with success used both for multiparametrical monitoring realization in clinic conditions and for electromagnetic conditions indication in residential or industrial premises, to be used as an instrument for revealing of the magnetodepending peoples and for other purposes.

(14)

7R6-M

USE OF DIAGNOSTIC MAGNETOMETERS AND MAGNETIC STORMS INDICATORS
IN CLINIC AS INFORMATION INSTRUMENT TO REVEALING
OF THE MAGNETODEPENDING PEOPLE

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Creation in the beginning of 90-th years experimental exemplar of small-sized and reliable diagnostic magnetometers (DM), capable to work in conditions with a large level of urban, has served as the beginning practical their uses in urban conditions. Created, later DM of a MAGIC- series and indicators of a magnetic storms (MSI) MF-01, MF-04 "MAGIC" and MF-05 successfully were used for realization electromagnetic monitoring in conditions of clinics of Moscow, Yalta and Kislovodsk sities. For example, DM, established in branch of reanimation Central Railway Hospital (CRH) No.3 of Moscow, has studied in a continuous mode more than six years. Use MSI in clinic has allowed us to produce the necessary recommendations for revealing and to treatment of the magnetodepending cardiological patients.

The use DM has allowed to organize multiparameter monitoring in clinic, that is to create an own continuous service tracings behind enclosing electromagnetic circumstances in real time. It, in turn, has allowed to have constantly datas about current disturbances of a magnetic field, in time to conduct therapy of the magnetodepending patients for want of beginning of a magnetic storms and to give necessary information in urban mass media.

Now in CRH No.3 is used small-sized automated digital system of data acquisition of a type IDL-04 (registrar of magnetic activity) "IMPEDANCE", which allows to conduct multiparameter monitoring of an environment on eight to measuring channels. The main measuring channel is the magnetometrical channel, and other measuring channels are used for connection of an electrical field, temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity sensors.

The experience, accumulated by us, has shown, that such gears can be are used as for realization of multiparameter monitoring in conditions of clinic, and for indication of electromagnetic circum- stances in usual residential or industrial premises to be used in quality of the tool for revealing of the magnetodepending people and for other purposes. The number of special computer programs is developed, permitting to conduct the correlation analysis of received physical parameters of an environment with some medic al datas. The outcomes of researches with magnetometers repeatedl\$ are published on various international conferences and open printing.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ МАГНИТОМЕТРОВ И ИНДИКАТОРОВ
МАГНИТНОЙ БУРИ В КЛИНИКЕ В КАЧЕСТВЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОГО
ИНСТРУМЕНТА ПО ВЫЯВЛЕНИЮ МАГНИТОЗАВИСИМЫХ ЛЮДЕЙ

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